

IPBES TCA Chapter 4. Review of literature on institutional misfits and inadequate policies / IPBES transformative change assessment

References selected from grey literature review

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GEF. 2016. Biodiversity mainstreaming in practice: a review of GEF experience

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T7 Task Force Climate and Environment. 2022. POLICY BRIEF Biodiversity protection through reward mechanisms and governance.

Abera & Abdulahi (eds.) 2015 (see ch 3 & 9)

Weston & King (2021)